

GENDER-DISCRIMINATORY NATIONALITY LAWS IN THE PERSIAN GULF STATES: ORIGIN, INFLUENCES AND IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract:

Gender-discriminatory nationality laws in the Persian Gulf states hinder women's ability to confer nationality on their children and foreign spouses, creating significant social and legal challenges. These laws reflect complex intersections of historical, cultural, and religious influences, sustaining gender biases that disproportionately impact women and families. This paper examines the gendered nature of the nationality laws along with the external and domestic factors contributing to their sustenance in the Persian Gulf states, having their far-reaching consequences for affected populations, including statelessness, limited access to healthcare, education, economic insecurity, etc. Stressing the urgency of reform, the paper also argues for eliminating gender-based discrimination in nationality laws to empower women with equal rights in nationality acquisition and transmission.

Keyword: Gender Discrimination, Nationality Laws, Persian Gulf States, Influences, Implications.

Introduction

The Persian Gulf, also known as the Arabian Gulf, is a Mediterranean Sea in Western Asia, that borders eight states - Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Qatar, United Arab Emirates, and Oman. Together these states contain 50 percent of the world's oil reserves with its export resulting in the accumulation of significant wealth. These states utilize their wealth by offering their citizens a range of comprehensive services, including developed infrastructure, healthcare services, employment

opportunities, recreational facilities, telecommunication services, etc. However, a high level of economic growth has not been able to translate into social development, particularly in the context of gender equality. Each Persian Gulf state predominantly follows the ‘paternal jus sanguinis’ system where nationality flows from fathers/husbands as opposed to ‘Jus soli’ citizenship based on birth. The principle of paternal jus sanguinis discriminates against women by restricting their ability to pass nationality to children and non-national spouses in contrast to male citizens who enjoy full citizenship rights. Such a discrepancy places women, children, and non-national spouses of the Gulf states in a precarious position by rendering them stateless and restricting their access to basic rights and services. While the origins of paternal jus sanguinis laws may be unclear, their persistence reflects complex intersections between historical, social, cultural, and religious influences which led to the continued sustenance of gender biasedness in the nationality laws of the Persian Gulf states. Some of these states have also introduced partial reforms to their nationality laws in response to growing international pressure yet ‘maternal jus sanguinis’ remains conditional, and women continue to face barriers in conferring nationality.

Therefore, this paper has made an attempt to explore various external and domestic factors influencing the patriarchal nationality laws of the Persian Gulf states, along with their drastic implications on the affected population. At the same time, an urgent need for reform has been emphasized to eliminate gender discrimination and empower women with equal rights to acquire, retain, and confer nationality on an equal basis with men.

Gendering Nationality

The European Convention on Nationality in its Article 2 defines nationality as “a legal bond between a person and a State” (European Convention on Nationality, 1997). At the same time, this relationship involves reciprocity of rights and duties. While the state grants a range of services, resources, social benefits, and fundamental rights to protect its citizens, the citizens also owe allegiance to the state and perform certain civic duties, including military service (in some countries), payment of taxes, or voting in elections. In this sense, the notion of allegiance to the state and protection by the state reflects a dominating role of ‘States’ in a citizen-state relationship where the ultimate authority

to decide who can be called ‘nationals’ rests with the state itself. As the Convention on Certain Questions relating to the Conflict of Nationality Law (1930) stated in Article 1: “It is for each State to determine under its own law who are its nationals. This law shall be recognised by other states in so far as it is consistent with international conventions, international custom, and the principles of law generally recognised with regard to nationality” (Convention on Certain Questions Relating to the Conflict of Nationality Law , 1930). Nationality as a principle is, therefore, regulated by domestic laws with states determining various modes of its acquisition.

Although different countries impose different criteria for acquiring nationality, there are two primary methods adopted by the states in general according to international law.

- Nationality by Birth (Jus Soli): Jus Soli, also known as the ‘Law of the Soil’ is a principle where nationality is acquired based on the place of birth. Under this system, a child born in a particular territory involuntarily acquires the nationality of that state irrespective of the status of his/her parents (Shearer & Opeskin, 2012).
- Nationality by Descent (Jus Sanguinis): The other involuntary criterion of nationality acquisition is Jus Sanguinis or the ‘Law of the Blood’ which requires nationality to pass from parental descent. The child, therefore, inherits the nationality of one or both parents regardless of the state where he or she was born (Shearer & Opeskin, 2012).

Having explained the modes of nationality acquisition it can be observed that Jus Soli is a more gender-neutral approach to nationality acquisition as it grants nationality solely based on birth whereas countries operating Jus Sanguinis nationality laws can “present particular risks for statelessness in women and their children” (Govil & Edwards, 2014, p. 175). This is primarily the case with the Persian Gulf countries following the jus sanguinis mode of nationality acquisition based on paternal descent. The ‘Paternal Jus Sanguinis’ system assumes the flow of nationality along the ‘male line’ implying that only fathers/husbands are entitled to pass their nationality to their children and spouses. In this way, the patriarchal nature of these laws discriminates against women by denying mothers/wives equal nationality rights, thereby restricting their

“ability to acquire, retain, and pass on their nationality to their children and their spouses.” (Beninger & Manjoo, 2023).

In this respect, Radha Govil and Alice Edwards (2014) have made significant efforts to analyse various circumstances of childhood statelessness when the inability of children to acquire their father’s citizenship can leave them without any nationality:

- Marriage to a stateless man: Women married to stateless men can result in the statelessness of the children as the father himself doesn’t hold a nationality to confer. Such a situation can perpetuate statelessness from one generation to another even if the mother is a national but restricted by laws to pass nationality.
- Birth out of marriage: When the state only allows fathers to confer nationality via paternal *jus sanguinis* laws, children born out of wedlock stand the risk of being stateless under various circumstances. For instance, if the father is unknown or abandons the mother before the child’s birth then the child will be born stateless. This situation may occur when female rape survivors are abandoned during pregnancy and later face challenges in proving paternity.
- Children born to non-national fathers: Another complex scenario that can potentially contribute to childhood statelessness is when the parents hold different nationalities. In a situation where the mother is a citizen of a state with ‘paternal *jus sanguinis*’ laws and the father belongs to a state having ‘*jus soli*’ nationality provisions, their child can become stateless under some circumstances such as:
 - a) If the child is born on the mother’s territory
 - b) If the family has a permanent residence in the mother’s state

In both situations, the child may not be able to inherit nationality from either parent. This is because the mother already lacks the right to confer nationality owing to the gendered nationality laws of her state, while the father’s foreign citizenship eliminates the possibility of conferring nationality by descent. At the same time, the child cannot claim the nationality of his father’s state due to the *jus soli* rule of the father’s country, which limits citizenship to those born within the territory (child was born in mother’s state). Therefore, the complex interplay of

nationality laws between parents' respective states may ultimately render their children stateless.

- Administrative barriers: Sometimes the inability of fathers to fulfil the administrative requirements including the birth registration of their children can also leave their children stateless. This could be particularly possible if the father has died or abandoned the family after marriage. Without proper birth registration, it becomes difficult to prove paternity, and thus, unregistered children become more susceptible to statelessness under *jus sanguinis* laws.

Moreover, gender-discriminatory nationality provisions are equally challenging for non-national spouses. In some countries where paternal *jus sanguinis* laws are followed, female citizens frequently encounter restrictions in conferring nationality to their foreign husbands in contrast to male citizens who do not have to face such restrictions. Such discriminatory provisions foster gender inequality and increase the risk of statelessness among male non-national spouses. For instance, the inability of a wife to transfer her nationality can leave her foreign husband stateless if he wishes to permanently settle in her state (for work or otherwise). At the same time, foreign female spouses married to male citizens of countries having gender discriminatory laws can be left temporarily stateless unless her husband's state immediately grants her nationality (Govil & Edwards, 2014).

Since the procedures to obtain a foreign citizenship are often stringent, complex, and time-consuming, it may take months or sometimes years before the application is finally approved. Even after obtaining nationality, foreign female spouses may still face the risk of statelessness if their marital status changes through divorce or the death of husbands (UN, 2014). In the absence of just and equal provisions of nationality conferral, foreign spouses may have to rely on Naturalisation as the second-best option to acquire nationality. However, the complexity of naturalisation procedures further reduces the possibility of nationality acquisition. Many Persian Gulf states often demand foreigners to fulfil a wide range of citizenship requirements to ensure cultural homogeneity with the existing nationals. For example, Kuwait's nationality laws require foreigners to have a minimum of 20 years of consecutive residence, knowledge of the Arabic language, Islam as a practicing

religion, and possession of necessary qualifications to obtain citizenship via naturalization (Art4, 1959).

In this manner, the paternal *jus sanguinis* system not only denies women equal nationality rights but also causes prolonged hardships for stateless children, spouses, and families by depriving them of all those privileges which are exclusively enjoyed by citizens. Thus, gender-based discrimination in nationality laws is an issue of human rights as much as it is of gender equality.

Origin and Influences

Although there is no uniform approach to trace the origin of gender discrimination, the following external and internal factors have been commonly acknowledged by various scholars that shaped the gender-discriminatory nationality legislation of the Persian Gulf states:

Ottoman Legacy: The Ottoman Empire ruled prominent parts of the Arabian Peninsula from the early modern period till 1918. This was also a period of European expansionism when the British and French imperial powers constantly tried to intervene and erode Ottoman sovereignty to access maritime trade (Hashmi & Augenstein, 2024). As a response, the ‘Law of Ottoman Nationality’ was enacted in 1869 to assert control over its subjects and limit the influx of colonial settlers. However, the law itself was predominantly influenced by the prevailing ‘*Jus Sanguinis*’ principle of the 1804 French Civil Code as various leading Arab jurists earned doctoral degrees in France during the 19th century (Parolin, 2009). Consequently, the gender-biased paternal *jus sanguinis* system became prevalent under Ottoman reign which only allowed children born to an Ottoman father and mother, or only of an Ottoman father, to be considered Ottoman subjects (Ottoman Law of Nationality, 1869, p. Art 1). With regard to children born to foreign parents on Ottoman soil, nationality could be acquired three years after attaining majority age (Ottoman Law of Nationality, 1869, p. Art 2). Such provisions aimed to solidify the Arab population against the rising imperial occupation in the 19th century. Moreover, the contemporary Gulf states continue to uphold the legacy of Ottoman law with its strict ‘*Jus Sanguinis*’ framework intends to safeguard Arab identity by resisting foreign integration.

Colonial Rule: Following the dissolution of the Ottoman Empire in the aftermath of World War I, the European colonial powers gained control of the Middle Eastern and North African (MENA) region. While the British mandate in Iraq was formally sanctioned by League of Nations, the rest of the Persian Gulf states got under the de facto control of British colonial rule (Waas & Albarazi, 2016). In these states, the imperial government introduced a set of patriarchal citizenship rules that was largely derived from the British Common law and Civil law system. The British Common law emphasized the significance of unity of nationality within the family implying that “every member of the family should have the same nationality – that of the husband or father” (Govil & Edwards, 2014, p. 172). The rationale behind the concept was the belief that a shared nationality would prevent conflicts of loyalties both within the family and in relation to the state. Similarly, the doctrine of ‘coverture’ under the Common law assumed the subordinate status of a married woman in relation to her husband who was regarded as a ‘baron’ or ‘lord’ under whose protection the legal rights and duties of women were dependent (Blackstone, 1753, p. 279). The absence of women’s individual identity along with the presumption of male as the breadwinner in the common law reinforced the notion of a married woman’s ‘dependent nationality.’ Such patriarchal values embedded in the colonial legal tradition subsequently found expression in the post-colonial nationality laws of Gulf states, reinforcing the ‘dependent’ nature of wives and their incapacity to confer nationality to their children (Govil & Edwards, 2014, p. 174).

Besides external factors, some scholars also attribute the persistence of patriarchal nationality laws to the following social, cultural, and economic characteristics of Arab societies:

Religious Influence: Religion has always played a pivotal role in Middle Eastern politics. Since Islam is the dominant religion, the Gulf states rely on *Sharia* as the basis for their gendered nationality laws. However, religious scholars are often divided on Islam’s position on women’s nationality rights (Waas & Albarazi, 2016). Conservative scholars, such as Murtaza Mutahhari of Iran stressed the biological differences between men and women to justify legal differentiation between the two genders (Emon, 2013). According to him, “Woman and man, on the basis of the very fact that one is a woman and the other is a man, are not identical with each other in many respects...this requires

that in very many rights, duties, and punishments they should not have an identical placing” (Mutahhari, 2009, p. 261). Such an interpretation extends women’s perceived inferiority from the natural to social and political domains, thereby denying them equal legal rights vis-à-vis men. Conversely, Modernist scholars hold flexible positions on nationality and criticize the conservative misinterpretation of Sharia laws that support the patriarchal status quo. As Shaheen Sardar Ali opines, “the Sharia grants both men and women the full freedom to choose or retain any nationality they want and to confer this nationality on their children. Although in Islam sons and daughters must take on their father’s name, this does not restrict their parents’ right to nationality” (Ali, 2006, p. 349).

Family Laws: Unlike the Western/European states where an individual is the basic unit of society, the Arab states identify the family as the basic unit of society. It is one of the core social institutions and its crucial aspects including marriage, divorce, inheritance, child custody, etc are regulated by Family Law (personal status code) (Joseph, 2010). In Arab states, the source of Family law is religious law that justifies patriarchal family structure in the name of religion. Some Arab jurists also cite specific verses from the Quran to rationalize men’s authority over women. One of the most critical verses in Chapter 4 that addresses men as ‘protectors’ or ‘guardians’ of women is often invoked for the legal elaboration of man as the ‘Head’ and woman as ‘Dependent’ within the family. Although this interpretation was strictly restricted to familial relationships, the domestic authority of men over women inevitably resonated outside the domestic sphere (Tucker, 2008). Consequently, the Arab states recognise male patriarchs as citizens in the political sphere while women’s political identity depends on their husbands/fathers. In this manner, the codification of family law in the Gulf states reiterates the unequal status of women as citizens. Thus, women came to be defined as ‘secondary citizens’ in these states as their status of being called a ‘citizen’ depends on their relation with the male member of the family (Joseph, 2010, p. 12).

Reserved State Benefits: A significant economic attribute that implicitly reinforces the ‘exclusionary’ nature of Gulf citizenship is the limited distribution of state benefits. Owing to their heavy reliance on oil exports, the Persian Gulf states are often called ‘rentier states’ where the large-scale revenues generated from the export of natural resources, particularly oil, are controlled by a small governing elite (Hashmi &

Augenstein, 2024). The social benefits of wealth generated by these rentier states are distributed exclusively among the legal citizens in the form of free education, guaranteed public sector employment, health care, free electricity and water, subsidized housing, etc. Such welfare services tend to exhaust the financial capabilities of these states, making them reluctant to expand their pool of beneficiaries. In this way, the exclusionary ‘jus sanguinis’ provision serves to differentiate naturalized citizens, migrant workers, and non-resident foreigners from the ‘originals’ (Indigenous population), thereby restricting their access to state-sponsored services. Therefore, the reluctance of Gulf states to integrate foreigners into the body of originals to limit their access to public services has also contributed to the sustenance of discriminatory nationality laws (Baldwin-Edwards, 2024).

Implications and Consequences

Gender-based discrimination in Gulf nationality laws can severely affect the lives of those who are rendered stateless by the effect of such laws. Without nationality, women, children, and non-national spouses might face obstacles and challenges in accessing the basic rights and state services necessary for human sustenance. Some of the following implications of gender-discriminatory nationality laws can be:

Creation, Perpetuation, Prolongation of Statelessness: The most fundamental and direct implication is statelessness particularly emanating from the ‘paternal jus sanguinis’ principle that devoid mothers of their right to pass nationality to their children. For instance, a child born to a Qatari national mother is not entitled to inherit her nationality under any circumstances, therefore childhood statelessness is the most likely outcome in case the father is not alive, unknown, stateless, or a non-national foreigner. While female stateless children have the option of acquiring nationality from their Qatari husbands after marriage, for male stateless children “the perpetuation of statelessness is an inevitable consequence and can even expand over time as every stateless male child at least is likely to, in turn, transmit his statelessness to the following generation” (Waas & Albarazi, 2016, p. 204). Likewise, foreign male spouses face the risk of statelessness, as Gulf national wives cannot transfer their nationality. In such cases, naturalisation seems a plausible option to resolve statelessness, however, stringent requirements of language, property, residence, and other bureaucratic

barriers can result in the extension or continuation of a person's stateless condition for a long period before he finally acquires the nationality. Therefore, gendered nationality laws not only create statelessness but also lead to its prolongation (Waas & Albarazi, 2016, p. 205).

Obstacles to Education, Employment, Healthcare: Gender-discriminatory nationality laws impede children's access to a whole range of basic rights, including, education, healthcare, and other social services. This is particularly challenging for stateless children, including those born to foreign fathers as they are denied access to state-sponsored education owing to the lack of nationality. In public schools too, these children are not admitted until all children with citizenship are registered (Global Campaign for Equal Nationality Rights). At the university level, stateless children of cross-national marriages are placed under the same category as foreign students where they compete for limited seats with higher tuition fees (CRTD, 2004). Subsequently, the absence of educational opportunities inadvertently produces barriers to formal employment. At the same time, the reservation of public sector employment for the Gulf nationals limits the employment opportunities for foreign spouses. In Saudi Arabia, for instance, foreign women are not permitted to work in clothing stores as these jobs are reserved for only Saudi women. Similarly, only Saudis can be employed as human resource managers, private security guards, cellular telephone workers, and hotel receptionists (Guzansky, 2021). Likewise, discriminatory nationality laws can also restrict access to state-sponsored healthcare facilities for those who lack the necessary identity documents required to receive such services. As a result, diseased and marginalised stateless individuals may be forced to seek treatment at private hospitals beyond their financial capacity. At the same time, the higher costs of private healthcare can also increase the occurrence of untreated diseases and inhibit preventative healthcare interventions (Global Campaign for Equal Nationality Rights).

Residency Problem: Having nationality proof including ID cards, passports, and other relevant documents enables citizens to reside in a state as long as they wish to. However, no such right is granted to stateless individuals, impeding their ability to secure permanent residence in any state. In some Gulf states, such as Saudi Arabia, Qatar, and Kuwait national women are not allowed to sponsor their stateless or non-national husbands for permanent residency, leaving them with no

choice but to live in the country illegally. Even if women can sponsor residency, the stateless husbands may be required to fulfil certain requirements of adequate employment, income, or housing which again can be difficult to meet due to their lack of nationality. Even after obtaining residency permits, stateless individuals are also sometimes required to renew their residency application which could be a costly and time-consuming process that further increases the chances of application rejection (Zahra Albarazi, 2013, p. 16). Moreover, individuals unable to secure legal residency owing to discriminatory nationality laws may face a constant threat of deportation, especially foreign spouses and children as “the state refuses to offer them the ‘right to residence’ in a country that denies responsibility for them” (Zahra Albarazi, 2013, p. 18).

Property rights and Inheritance: Property rights in the Gulf states are only accorded to the citizens while the non-citizens (foreigners and stateless persons) may lack the ability to own or inherit property. Accordingly, children of national women married to foreign fathers are restricted from inheriting their mother’s property owing to the gendered laws. Therefore, a female national holding registered property may not be able to bequeath it to her children or husband upon her death (Zahra Albarazi, 2013, p. 19). In some Gulf states where only the children of divorced women are liable to inherit property, national mothers are compelled to divorce their stateless/foreign husbands to resolve the issue. For example, Kuwaiti mothers having stateless children as a result of marrying non-nationals, sometimes beg their husbands to divorce them as it is the only way their children can be registered as citizens, and become entitled to property rights (Waas, Albaraz, & Brennan, 2019).

Women’s Vulnerability: There is also growing evidence that women are both more vulnerable to becoming stateless, and more vulnerable when stateless. Although there is limited existing research that focuses on the impacts of gender discriminatory laws and stateless specifically on women, emerging research suggests that stateless women are especially vulnerable to gender-based violence including sexual exploitation, domestic violence, trafficking, etc (Beninger & Manjoo, 2023). When nationality flows from husbands, foreign female spouses in such countries may have to tolerate domestic abuse due to the fear of losing citizenship if their husband abandons her. Moreover, a greater risk of human trafficking exists among stateless women and girls. Shaheen

also highlights the increased incidents of gender-based violence in countries with discriminatory laws where stateless women find it difficult to enter the labour force, and therefore resort to inappropriate measures of living, such as prostitution, risking physical abuse, sexual exploitation, sexual assault, abduction, or disappearance (Shaheen, 2018). Additionally, the inability of women to pass nationality to their children psychologically distress mothers who feel guilty for stripping away their children's basic rights by marrying foreigners/stateless.

Need for Reforms

In light of the above implications of gender discriminatory laws, it is crucial to analyse why statelessness is a pressing issue that seeks immediate regional and global attention and why reforms in national legislation are needed to tackle statelessness.

Hannah Arendt in her seminal work *Origins of Totalitarianism* (1951) explained that stateless people experience three types of loss: the loss of a home where they were born, the loss of government protection, and the loss of a place in the world i.e. political community “which makes opinions significant and actions effective” (Arendt, 1956, p. 296). This analysis is relevant to understanding the plight of stateless people; however, Arendt's arguments should be understood within the context of interwar Europe, where forced migration and expulsion compelled many people to leave their homeland. In contemporary times, statelessness does not necessarily result from migration or expulsion, rather it can be observed among people who live in the same place from birth till death. Gender-discriminatory nationality laws are one such cause of statelessness where stateless people lack recognition and citizenship in the same country where they live or have always lived (Gibney, 2014). Reforming the nationality laws, therefore, becomes imperative to resolve the problem of statelessness emanating from such laws.

At the international level, there are two UN Conventions that primarily deal with the problem of statelessness. The 1954 Convention ensures that stateless people are given the same treatment and basic rights such as education, freedom of religion, etc, as citizens (Convention Relating to the Status of Stateless Persons, 1954). The 1961 Convention, on the other hand, aims to reduce and avoid various scenarios where statelessness can occur including statelessness at birth by requiring

States to grant citizenship to children born on the territory (Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness, 1961). Both these conventions allow states to determine their nationality laws and have significant gender gaps. The 1954 Convention fails to recognise gender discrimination in the provision of rights as its Article 3 directs State parties to apply the provisions of this Convention to stateless persons without any discrimination of religion, race, or country of origin. The other Convention (1961) does allow children to get nationality from their mothers, but this only applies in cases where the child is born in wedlock. Thus, the Statelessness Conventions do not challenge the direct gender discrimination rooted in nationality laws (Beninger & Manjoo, 2023). In this direction, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) is a landmark treaty that was adopted by UNGA in 1979 and later entered into force in 1981. It is the most comprehensive treaty that specifically prohibits gender discrimination in nationality laws and also requires states to initiate reforms in their national constitutions or other appropriate legislation to ensure the practical realization of equality between men and women. Addressing the provision of nationality, Article 9 (1) of CEDAW requires states parties to grant women equal rights with men to acquire, change, or retain their nationality. It further states that “neither marriage to an alien nor change of nationality by the husband during marriage shall automatically change the nationality of the wife, render her stateless or force upon her the nationality of the husband” (CEDAW, 1979, p. Art 9 (1)). To prevent instances of childhood statelessness, it also directs states parties to grant women equal rights with men with respect to the nationality of their children. States that are parties to CEDAW are obligated to take measures and bring reforms to eliminate discrimination against women in all areas, including nationality laws.

All seven Persian Gulf states are party to CEDAW, with Iran being the only exception. However, these states have made explicit reservations, particularly to Article 9 as it has been perceived as conflicting with countries’ religious law (Sharia) and traditional gender roles. Accordingly, some of these states have only initiated partial nationality reforms, while others have made no changes at all. For instance, Bahrain, Oman, Saudi Arabia, and UAE allow women to confer nationality to children under certain conditions, for example, if the father is stateless or unknown but not if he’s a foreigner (Global Campaign for

Equal Nationality Rights). Similarly, Iran and Iraq have also made amendments to allow children of foreign fathers to apply for citizenship. However, it is important to note that the conferral of nationality by mothers in these situations is not automatic; rather, it requires an application process that can be lengthy and complicated, with no guarantee of approval. Furthermore, Kuwait and Qatar have the most stringent nationality laws, as they do not permit women to confer nationality to their children or spouses under any circumstances. Such reservations, therefore, ensure that Persian Gulf states are not held accountable for maintaining a gendered *jus sanguinis* regime despite their CEDAW commitments (Waas & Albarazi, 2016, p. 239).

In this manner, the complete eradication of gender biases from the nationality laws of the Gulf states is the only way by which absolute parity can be ensured between men and women in the acquisition, retention, and conferral of nationality. This is only possible if the states “withdraw their reservations to Article 9 of CEDAW and draft new legislation permitting equal nationality opportunities for men and women within their borders” (Shaheen, 2018, p. 15). Moreover, the role of civil society, human rights activists, and UN agencies such as UNHCR and UNICEF is vitally important in advocating for nationality reforms to prevent statelessness in general and to address human rights violations in particular, caused by such discriminatory laws.

Conclusion

Gender-discriminatory nationality laws in the Persian Gulf states reflect deeply entrenched cultural, historical, and legal norms that perpetuate inequality and restrict women's rights. These laws not only limit women's ability to confer nationality to their children and foreign spouses but also have broader implications for social stability, family cohesion, and economic well-being. The resulting statelessness and marginalization of affected populations underscore the urgent need for reform. International pressure and advocacy from local activists have begun to pave the way for change, but substantial hurdles remain. Strict implementation of CEDAW to ensure equal rights for women in acquiring, retaining, and conferring nationality is a critical step toward dismantling systemic gender biases and enhancing women's autonomy.

As the Persian Gulf states continue to navigate modernity and globalization, embracing gender-inclusive nationality laws can contribute to social progress, economic development, and improved international standing. Ultimately, achieving equitable nationality rights will not only benefit women and their families but also promote broader societal stability and harmony in the region. It is imperative for policymakers to prioritize these reforms as a fundamental aspect of advancing human rights and equality.

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